

1 Is it all about money? A perspective on volunteer 2 and paid contributors from The Turing Way 3 community via a qualitative registered report 4

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18 **Data sharing**

19 Once generated, de-identified data is available at *Zenodo* [*link to DOI*].

20 **Conflict of interest**

21 EP, DB are members of The Turing Way Community. EP has been (partially) supported
22 institutionally for her contributions to the Turing Way (part of their working hours/job
23 description). EP and DB have not received direct financial compensation from The Turing
24 Way for their involvements, nor has the work on this manuscript been financially supported
25 by The Turing Way.

26 **Ethics**

27 This study has undergone extensive community review, of which the materials are
28 available in **Appendix C**. The community was consulted and asked for input along the

29 entire way of the project via GitHub discussions and online community sessions (with a
30 focus on the ethics procedures on 19 March 2025). This study will follow
31 recommendations set out by the University of Aruba and The Alan Turing Institute, and data
32 processing will be in line with the GDPR. An ethics application is currently pending
33 approval at the University of Aruba.

34 Abstract

35 Open Source Software (OSS) projects are typically open to, and dependent on, volunteer
36 contributions. This study examines how financial support – or the lack thereof – may
37 influence contributions to OSS projects. It takes *The Turing Way* as a case study. The Turing
38 Way is an open source book and community focused on best practices in inclusive and
39 reproducible data science. The Turing Way presents a particularly interesting case: from its
40 inception in 2019 until June 2025, it received institutional support from The Alan Turing
41 Institute (UK). A broader range of individuals also contribute on a voluntary basis to both
42 the community and the book, with over 500 acknowledged contributors in 2026.

43 This study adopts a critical realist approach to examine whether financial compensation
44 leads to differences in how contributors engage with The Turing Way. The distinction
45 between paid and volunteer contributions is, however, often blurred within this
46 community. To address this, the study first identifies how community members define
47 ‘being (financially) compensated’ through an online survey. The survey findings will then be
48 discussed with the community in an online focus group. Building on these insights, the
49 study will conduct semi-structured interviews with community members across a
50 continuum from ‘volunteer’ to ‘compensated’ to ‘financially compensated’, in order to
51 generate rich, in-depth insights into contributors’ lived experiences using reflexive
52 thematic analysis. The interviews will also explore the community dynamics that arise from
53 these differing forms of engagement. Preliminary findings from the interviews will be
54 shared and discussed with the community in a second online focus group.

55 *[results/discussion summary placeholder]*

56 The results may offer insights into potentially unwanted community dynamics to avoid
57 within OSS ecosystems, as well as highlight best practices to foster. In doing so, the study
58 contributes to ongoing discussions on how to ensure the long-term sustainability of OSS
59 communities – a common challenge across such projects.

60 **Keywords:** Paid contributors, volunteer contributors, Open Source, Open Source
61 community, Open Science, recognition and rewards

62 1 Introduction

63 Open source software (OSS) has become a critical component of society's software
64 infrastructure, with many projects hosted on platforms that enable users and contributors
65 to engage closely with both the project and its surrounding community (Eghbal, 2020).
66 Although these projects are, in principle, open to anyone, contributors are often not
67 directly compensated for their work (Meluso et al., 2025; Krishnamurthy et al., 2024; Riehle
68 et al., 2014; Zhang et al., 2024). This lack of financial compensation may inhibit individuals
69 who wish to contribute but have limited time to do so on a voluntary basis (Buytaert, 2019).

70 The fallacy of free time and meritocracy in open source communities frequently leads to a
71 lack of diversity among contributors (Buytaert, 2019; Dryden, 2013), as well as burnout
72 among existing contributors (Heath, 2025). Even when companies encourage employees
73 to contribute to OSS projects during working hours, these challenges may persist
74 (Buytaert, 2019; Heath, 2025). A decline in contributor numbers and diversity negatively
75 affects the sustainability of OSS projects. Given the critical role of OSS in modern software
76 infrastructure, it is therefore essential to ensure that contributors are adequately
77 supported and recognised.

78 Financial support, rewards and incentives can help address these challenges by enabling
79 broader participation in OSS projects (Atiq & Tripathi, 2016; Heath, 2025; Lange et al.
80 2025). Several organisations and initiatives already advocate for compensating OSS
81 contributors – such as [thanks.dev](#), [Open Source Pledge](#), [Open Source Endowment](#), [Github](#)
82 [Sponsors](#), [Open Collective](#), [Tidelift](#), [CHAOSS Labor Investment metric](#), [Google Summer of](#)
83 [Code](#), and [Outreachy](#). Nevertheless, the impact of financial support on OSS projects and
84 communities remains underexplored (Atiq & Tripathi, 2016; Lakhani & Wolf, 2005; Zhang et
85 al., 2024).

86 This type of research is needed, as motivation crowding theory suggests that introducing
87 monetary rewards into systems may not always produce the intended outcomes (Frey &
88 Jegen, 2001; Meluso et al., 2025). For instance, external interventions such as financial
89 rewards may crowd out intrinsic motivation if they are perceived as controlling. However,
90 when interventions are perceived as supportive, they may crowd in intrinsic motivation
91 (Frey & Jegen, 2001). Atiq and Tripathi (2016, p. 1) already illustrated that '*fair-terms,*
92 *transparency and effective communication practices are essential*' as compensations that
93 are not transparent and community orientated may alienate volunteers from the
94 community.

95 This is important to consider, as most participants in the OSS ecosystem do not receive
96 direct payments or dedicated working time (Lakhani & Wolf, 2005). Instead, not all

97 contributors may be motivated by direct financial compensation (Alexy & Leitner, 2011;
98 Jahn et al., 2024; Wu et al., 2011), and some actively oppose the introduction of
99 compensation into the OSS ecosystem (Krishnamurthy et al., 2014; Meluso et al., 2025).
100 This resistance may stem from the strong culture of reciprocity on which OSS communities
101 are built (Shah, 2006; Wu et al., 2011). Nevertheless, there is evidence that compensated
102 contributors may have more time available to contribute to projects compared to
103 volunteers (Atiq & Tripathi, 2016; Krishnamurthy et al., 2014; Lakhani & Wolf, 2005; Roberts
104 et al., 2006; Zhang et al., 2024). Previous research also suggests that many OSS
105 developers are open to compensation, provided it is not perceived as controlling (Atiq &
106 Tripathi, 2016; Krishnamurthy et al., 2014). As compensated contributions may lead to
107 more frequent or more complex contributions, compensation could play an important role
108 in supporting the progress and long-term sustainability of OSS development.

109 Previous research on open source software and open science communities has identified
110 differences among contributors in terms of the number of contributions they make, the
111 size and complexity of the contributions, the duration of acceptance of contributions, and
112 the likelihood rejections of contributions (Dias et al., 2018; Zhang et al., 2024). These
113 differences may also be reflected in the types of roles contributors assume within projects.
114 For example, paid contributors may be more likely to engage in activities such as reviewing
115 contributions or developing complex code (Dias et al., 2018), or be responsible for ‘grunt
116 work’ (Alexy & Leitner, 2011; Atiq & Tripathi, 2016; Lange et al., 2025; Zhang et al., 2024).
117 On the other hand, volunteer contributors may be involved more often in low effort tasks
118 (Dias et al., 2018; Pinto et al., 2016) or are more flexible about which tasks they choose and
119 when they work on them, aligning their contributions with personal interest or availability
120 (Roberts et al., 2006; Shah, 2006).

121 These differences in roles and engagement are closely linked to variations in motivation.
122 Paid contributors may be driven by work-related user needs and professional status,
123 whereas volunteers are motivated by skill development, personal interest, or the need to
124 use the software for non-work purposes (Lakhani & Wolf, 2005). For a broader overview of
125 motivations to contribute to OSS projects, see Von Krogh et al. (2012).

126 To study the impact of financial support on OSS projects and communities this research
127 will focus on a specific open source community: The Turing Way. While this study is
128 focused specifically on OSS ecosystems, insights may also be applicable to other
129 knowledge-sharing ecosystems with volunteer contributors.

130 1.1 The Turing Way

131 The Turing Way (TTW) is an Open Source Software (OSS) and Open Science project focused
132 on making data science more collaborative, inclusive, ethical and reproducible. The
133 project was launched in 2019 as a guide to research reproducibility and has since then
134 expanded into a series of guides on Reproducible Research, Project Design,
135 Communication, Collaboration and Ethical Research. The guidance and
136 recommendations in these guides are co-authored by contributors from diverse
137 backgrounds, including students, researchers, educators, community leaders, and policy-
138 makers who bring both lived experience and domain knowledge. These contributors work
139 towards The Turing Way’s moonshot goal: to “make reproducibility too easy not to do”.
140 Achieving this goal relies on open collaboration and community-driven processes.

141 A core principle of TTW is therefore its commitment to inclusivity and openness to a wide
142 range of possible contributors. To support this, the community has established contributor
143 guidelines (The Turing Way Community, 2025c), a code of conduct (The Turing Way
144 Community, 2025b), and formal processes to acknowledge contributions to both the
145 community and the book (The Turing Way Community, 2025a). The barriers to contribute to
146 TTW are intentionally low. In the [contributing guidelines](#) (The Turing Way Community,
147 2025c) contributions ‘*include but are not limited to, bug fixing, chapter planning, writing,*
148 *editing, reviewing, idea generation, presentation, project management, and maintenance.*’
149 As a result, not all contributions are directly tied to code or content production, and more
150 indirect forms of participation are also highly valued.

151 Historically, TTW received financial support from The Alan Turing Institute through the
152 EPSRC grant EP/N510129/1, and the EPSRC Grant EP/T001569/1, particularly the "Tools,
153 Practices and Systems" theme. This support enabled 10-20 staff members to dedicate a
154 portion of their time (approximately 5%) to the project, alongside 2-3 full-time staff
155 members. In addition to institutional support from The Alan Turing Institute, several regular
156 contributors also received institutional support, enabling them to work on TTW during their
157 paid working hours. These institutions include TU Delft, the eScience Center, and Vrije
158 Universiteit Amsterdam in the Netherlands.

159 Since 2025, The Turing Way has entered a transition phase in which financial support has
160 become more limited. The reduction in financial stability may influence how contributors
161 experience recognition and support for their work.

162

163 1.2 Compensated contributions in The Turing Way

164 Questions around what constitutes ‘compensation’ have been central in early discussions
165 with The Turing Way community members, as compensation may take many forms. Under
166 ‘compensation’, we provisionally distinguish between two types to guide our investigation:
167 financial compensation and rewards. Within the first category, contributors may receive
168 direct financial payment as a result of their work with The Turing Way, such as salaries,
169 grants, bounties, crowd funding, donations and sponsorships. Financial support can also
170 be provided more indirectly, by ensuring funding to attend conferences, courses,
171 accessibility or equipment. Contributors may additionally receive institutional support in
172 the form of allocated working time.

173 Rewards include non-financial benefits, such as skill development, professional
174 recognition, networking, increased visibility, enjoyment derived from interactions and
175 contributions, and enhanced community status.

176 However, the boundaries between these categories are often blurred, and how
177 compensation is defined and perceived varies between contributors, representing the
178 starting point of this research.

179 To better understand how different forms of compensation influence participation and the
180 dynamics between contributors within The Turing Way community, this study first
181 investigates how The Turing Way contributors define and experience compensation
182 through a survey. Survey data will be analysed to map patterns in perceived forms of
183 compensation, while the dynamics between different types of contributors are explored
184 through two focus groups and one-to-one in-depth interviews examining perceived
185 differences between compensated and volunteer contributions. More details on the data
186 collection and analysis processes are provided under section 2: Data Collection.

187 This study is conducted through a critical realist lens (Bhaskay, 2016; Maxwell, 2012)
188 applied to Thematic Analysis (TA), drawing inspiration from Fryer 2022’s five-step
189 approach. It aims to identify the mechanisms that enable or constrain participation in open
190 source and open science communities such as TTW, as well as the causal explanations
191 underlying dynamics in these communities. The results will inform strategies for
192 supporting both compensated and volunteer contributors, with the ultimate goal of
193 reducing inequalities between these groups and promoting the long-term sustainability of
194 the project. The findings will contribute to improving TTW’s contribution and recognition
195 processes and will also be shared publicly to support other OSS communities facing
196 similar challenges, thus contributing positively to the wider ecosystem.

197 The research questions are as following:

- 198 • What forms does compensation take in The Turing Way (for example, financial
199 compensation, training, mentoring, visibility, time), and how are these experienced
200 by contributors?
- 201 • How do different forms of compensation influence the dynamics between different
202 types of contributors (such as volunteer and paid contributors)?
- 203 • How do social and structural factors (for example, gender, geographic location,
204 employment status) shape individuals' ability to contribute to open source and
205 open science communities?

206 A critical realist approach to TA supports the explanatory aims of this study. While
207 exploratory approaches to TA are valuable for describing phenomena in under-researched
208 contexts, critical realism emphasises the importance of moving beyond description to
209 develop causal explanations of observed patterns. In line with Fryer (2022), this approach
210 is therefore well suited to research contexts where the focus is on identifying underlying
211 mechanisms that generate particular social dynamics. Given that participation in open
212 source and open science communities, and related challenges, have been widely
213 documented, this study seeks not only to describe forms of compensation, but to explain
214 how and why these shape participation, inequalities, and contributor experiences within
215 The Turing Way.

216 1.3 Reflexivity Statement

217 The authors take a critical realism approach. Critical realism conceptualises stratified
218 realities in which multiple perspectives, interpretations and representations provide partial
219 access to an underlying reality (Bhaskay, 2016; Braun & Clarke, 2022; Maxwell, 2012;
220 Willis, 2023). Critical realism is particularly suited to this study as it allows for the
221 examination of structural forces and generative mechanisms that shape contributors'
222 behaviour, while also accounting for individual agency and the subjective meanings
223 contributors attach to their engagement.

224 These perspectives and interpretations are influenced by dynamic, historically situated,
225 social relations and agentic contexts (Greenhalgh & Manzano, 2022), as well as by the
226 positionalities of both researchers and participants. Both authors are part of The Turing
227 Way and have been institutionally supported for their work, although at different levels (EP:
228 2020-present, 1-2 working hours dedicated per week; DB: 2023-present, no hours
229 exclusively dedicated, but work adjacent to TTW allowed her to make contributions during
230 her working hours). Their positions may therefore influence the data collection and
231 interpretation processes. The authors outline their background and context in more
232 detailed reflexivity notes in **Appendix A**. The authors will also maintain a reflexivity journal

233 from the beginning of data collection until the end of the data analysis, to record the
234 thoughts and doubts they encounter during these processes. The authors will furthermore
235 regularly meet during the different stages of the project. More details are available in
236 **Appendix A5.**

237 2 Data collection

238 2.1 Participants

239 2.1.1 The Turing Way Community

240 The Turing Way can be described as a federation (Eghbal, 2020), with over 500 contributors
241 and a core group of approximately 25 individuals who are more closely involved in project
242 maintenance and coordination. This core group is organised into working groups, each
243 responsible for specific areas such as community support, accessibility, fundraising,
244 infrastructure maintenance, and event organisation. Working groups typically consist of 2-
245 6 members, and some individuals participate in multiple groups. These working groups
246 operate at an organisational level that supports the overall sustainability of the project.
247 Each group is led by one or more chairs, who also participate in the Steering Committee.
248 The steering committee is responsible for decisions that affect the project as a whole or
249 extend beyond the scope of individual working groups. However, decisions are made
250 transparently and are shared with the wider community for discussion.

251 The community primarily comes together via online calls. The Collaboration Café calls are
252 organised twice a month (every first and third Wednesday) and open to all contributors and
253 new community members. Collaboration Café calls last for two hours and can be seen as
254 a flexible co-working space (not everyone will always join the full two hours). The working
255 groups tend to meet for one hour, with their occurrence depending on the preferences of
256 the working group members (ranging from weekly to monthly). These working group calls
257 are more restricted and joined only by working group members or people interested in
258 joining the working group. During the Community Forum (typically a one hour long call) the
259 wider community comes together for updates and (decision making) discussions. The
260 TWW also hosts contributor events twice a year, known as Book Dashes, which take place
261 both online and in-person (UK, the Netherlands, Aruba). These events usually take place
262 over 2-5 days in May and November.

263 The current study will be the first community-wide study to determine community
264 demographics, focusing on the amount of paid and volunteer contributors to The Turing
265 Way.

266 **2.1.2 Recruitment channels**

267 The authors are taking several steps to ensure engagement with a diverse range of The
268 Turing Way contributors who align with the selection criteria (**Table 1**):

- 269 • Advertising the call for participation on all possible communication forums (TTW
270 newsletter, LinkedIn, Slack and during Community Calls). As the more public
271 channels, such as LinkedIn, are also accessible to people outside of The Turing Way
272 community, the call for participation will explain that study participation is open
273 only to individuals who have contributed to The Turing Way book or community (see
274 1.1 for examples of different types of contributions).
- 275 • Community members may also be actively approached by directly emailing or
276 messaging them. If members indicate that they are not interested in participation
277 they will no longer be actively recruited.
- 278 • Requesting that participants inform their peers in The Turing Way about the
279 opportunity to participate, encouraging them to think about people who might have
280 a unique or underrepresented view on the topics we cover (Crouse & Lowe, 2018;
281 Hancock & Gile, 2011).
- 282 • Attending The Turing Way Collaboration Café events to share intermediate findings
283 and make attendees aware of opportunities to participate.
- 284 • Seeking feedback on preliminary findings via The Turing Way GitHub repository
285 ([#3833](#)), which will include information on how to participate, and include
286 discussion points and feedback from the community that will inform the study.

287

288 **Table 1:** Inclusion criteria for participants in the various steps of the study.

Method	Criteria	Aimed participation	Considerations
Survey	Inclusion: Any TTW member that has contributed to TTW book and/or community. Exclusion: Data from individuals filling out the survey that have not contributed to TTW before will be omitted.	10% of the TTW contributors	Ensure representation of both actively engaged and past/inactive TTW members
Interviews	Inclusion: Any TTW member that has contributed to TTW book and/or community. Exclusion: Individuals who have not contributed to TTW book/community	10-20 TTW members	Approximately equal distribution of TTW members with different backgrounds (volunteer/paid or mixed contributor) and a variety of experience with TTW (new versus core project member)
Focus groups	Engagement with TTW members that have engaged actively with the research project via feedback sessions and/or have participated in the interviews, ideally an equal distribution of the backgrounds represented in the interviews.	4-10 TTW members, ideal target 8-10 participants per focus group.	

289 **2.2 Methods**

290 This study uses a mixed-methods approach to answer the research question (**Figure 1**).
 291 First, the study identifies what community members consider to be ‘being (financially)
 292 compensated ’ for their contributions via an online survey (2.2.1), resulting in quantitative
 293 data that will be analysed and provide the basis for the next steps in the study. The survey
 294 results will be discussed with The Turing Way community via an online focus group (2.2.3),
 295 which will provide additional insights and feedback to inform the questions for the semi-
 296 structured interviews (2.2.2), followed by a second focus group. The analysis will be
 297 iterative, with each stage building on the previous ones and informing the next, while
 298 allowing the authors to revisit earlier stages to compare and integrate insights.

299

300 **Figure 1:** Visual summary of the study steps, in the style of The Turing Way images. Image adapted from The
 301 Turing Way Community & Scriberia (2020).

302 2.2.1 Survey

303 This study employs a purposive sampling approach, targeting members of The Turing Way
 304 community, with survey participation based on voluntary response. The survey (**Appendix**
 305 **B1**) will be open to all The Turing Way community members who actively view the
 306 communication spaces used by the community (such as Slack, mailing lists, and GitHub).
 307 To facilitate participation, the survey and its questions are designed to take no longer than
 308 10 minutes to complete. As noted above, The Turing Way is a large, distributed community
 309 of over 500 contributors worldwide (567 as of April 6, 2026), but levels of engagement vary
 310 considerably, with some contributors participating only once, others contributing
 311 sporadically, and some dedicating time on a weekly basis. The survey therefore aims to
 312 achieve 50-100 responses. A minimum target of 50 responses is intended to ensure
 313 representation from the core group of approximately 25 highly engaged contributors,
 314 alongside less-engaged members who nevertheless contribute, or have contributed, to

315 TTW in various capacities. Reaching closer to 100 responses (approximately 10% of the
316 broader community, while accounting for inactive or outdated contacts) would provide a
317 sufficiently diverse and informative sample to identify patterns of engagement, forms of
318 compensation, and contributors' experiences. These insights will in turn inform the design
319 of subsequent focus groups and in-depth interviews.

320 The survey represents only one component of a mixed-methods approach. It is primarily
321 used to identify overarching patterns in engagement and compensation, informing the
322 design of subsequent qualitative phases that enable a deeper exploration of perceived
323 differences between volunteer contributions and those identified as compensated through
324 the analysis. If the response rate of the survey is unexpectedly low, additional outreach will
325 be conducted through more targeted, individual communication.

326 The survey was piloted with individuals from different backgrounds (a volunteer
327 contributor, a paid contributor, and a contributor with mixed volunteer/paid experience)
328 and varying levels of engagement with The Turing Way (new versus core project members).
329 Feedback was gathered individually, through a meeting with reviewers (23 April 2025), and
330 during Collaboration Cafés (4 June 2025 and 21 January 2026). Based on this feedback,
331 questions and accompanying information were revised to ensure clarity. This included
332 removing questions about career stage and demographics, which were found to be unclear
333 and overly focused on traditional academic roles (for example, Assistant Professor,
334 Postdoc), which do not always apply in OSS communities. Questions were also rephrased
335 to avoid assuming shared definitions of 'volunteer' and 'paid' contributors, as no
336 consensus existed on these terms. See **Appendix B2** for the full draft of the first version of
337 the survey.

338 Overall, the survey aims to:

- 339 ● Identify which respondents receive financial support for their contributions, and
340 whether they consider themselves as a paid or volunteer contributor;
- 341 ● Explore how contributors define what constitutes a compensated contribution;
- 342 ● Inform the selection of interview participants by capturing the extent and types of
343 financial support (based on responses to "*To what degree are your engagements
344 with The Turing Way financially supported?*"), where respondents have consented to
345 be contacted.

346 2.2.2 Interviews

347 After the survey data has been discussed in a focus group and the interview protocol has
348 been adjusted if needed, participants will be invited to take part in a semi-structured

349 interview. Individuals who indicate their willingness to be interviewed via the survey will be
350 considered, and a general call for participation will be distributed through the same
351 communication channels used to distribute the survey. Interview participants will then be
352 purposely selected to ensure diversity in terms of forms of compensation, contribution
353 experience, and demographic characteristics, based on the selection criteria outlined in
354 **Table 1**. To facilitate participation, participants will be offered time slots that align with
355 their availability and accommodate their work and personal responsibilities.

356 The semi structured interviews will be conducted to understand participants' definition of
357 'compensated contributions', and how this compensation (or lack thereof) may influence
358 the community dynamics of The Turing Way. Semi-structured interviews allow for a more
359 in-depth exploration of the topic, enabling participants to talk about their individual
360 experiences, including perceived barriers and enablers. See **Appendix C** for the full semi-
361 structured interview procedure.

362 The interview sample will aim to include an equal split of contributors with different levels
363 of financial support for their contributions. In addition, where possible, a balance will be
364 sought in terms of level of contribution experience (one time contributor versus leadership
365 roles), roles and self-reported demographics, depending on the availability of community
366 members. Participants will be asked to self-identify their role, duration and time-frame of
367 their participation in the community. The intention is to engage approximately 10-20
368 community members in the interview stage, aligning with the literature (Baker & Edwards,
369 2012; Braun & Clarke, 2022) on projects of similar sizes.

370 The semi-structured interviews will be piloted by conducting a pilot interview with 1-2
371 individuals and/or a self-interview between the two authors, after which the questions, or
372 the order/priority of questions, may be adapted.

373 Semi-structured interviews are intended to:

- 374 ● Refine and deepen the understanding of compensation (financial and non-financial)
375 for contributions as established by the survey data.
- 376 ● Clarify how different types of contributors feel supported or challenged when they
377 contribute to the Turing Way.
- 378 ● Identify in more detail what challenges contributors face and how this is related to
379 different types of compensation for their efforts.
- 380 ● Explore the impact of (direct) financial compensation on contributions and its
381 potential long-term effects on contributors and the community.

382 Semi-structured interviews will be conducted in English and will last approximately 45-60
383 minutes. Interviews will be audio recorded and transcribed (using Zoom/otter.ai if
384 transcription permission is given by the participant, otherwise manual transcription will be
385 conducted). Transcriptions will be checked against the recordings to ensure no data is
386 lost, after which the recordings will be deleted. As described in the informed consent form,
387 the recordings will be deleted at Stage 2 acceptance of the article.

388 Braun & Clarke's (2021; 2022) framework for reflexive thematic analysis and Fryer's (2022)
389 critical realist approach will guide the analysis of transcriptions. The purpose of thematic
390 analysis is to develop themes in the dataset in relation to the research question (Braun &
391 Clarke, 2022). This research takes an inductive approach where codes and themes are
392 developed through engagement with the data rather than determined by previous
393 research, as the project aims to explore the specific experiences of The Turing Way
394 community members.

395 In reflexive thematic analysis the researcher(s) is an active participant in meaning
396 construction, with codes deriving from the interactions between the researcher,
397 participants and the data (Braun & Clarke, 2021, 2022). The researcher's subjectivity
398 (**Appendix A**) "*sculpts the knowledge produced, rather than a must-be-contained threat to*
399 *credibility*" (Braun & Clarke, 2021, p. 8).

400 2.2.3 Focus groups

401 Two focus groups are planned to discuss the progress of the project with The Turing Way
402 community, and receive feedback on the author's interpretation of the data (**Appendix C**).

- 403 1. The first focus group will discuss the results of the survey and will provide an
404 opportunity to adjust the questions of the semi-structured interviews, if needed.
- 405 2. The second focus group will present the preliminary results of the semi-structured
406 interviews, share initial themes and interpretations and integrate participants'
407 perspectives.

408 Only two focus groups will be held to avoid fragmentation of participants and participation
409 fatigue. Individual invites will be sent to community members that have engaged actively
410 with the project (such as the reviewers and attendees of previous feedback calls). Each
411 focus group will include a minimum of four participants, with a target of 8-10 individuals.
412 The focus group meetings will be recorded and transcribed following the same process as
413 the interviews. Permission for the recording and transcription will be obtained prior to the
414 start of each focus group. If participants do not consent, they will be invited to contribute
415 asynchronously instead. If fewer than four individuals are available for the focus groups,
416 the sessions will be rescheduled.

417 Community members who are unable to participate in the focus groups, or do not wish
418 to be recorded, can still provide asynchronous input via Slack or the dedicated GitHub
419 discussion threads ([#4603](#) and [#4604](#)).

420 2.3 Ethics

421 This study took a community-driven approach as The Turing Way is a privacy-sensitive
422 community with many contributors who are experts in ethics, data protection and the
423 management of sensitive data. The entire community was notified of the ethical
424 procedures of the project (see **Appendix D** for details) and was able to provide input via
425 several routes: 1) A GitHub issue [#3833](#) (the primary communication channel within the
426 Turing Way), 2) community wide meetings during the Collaboration Cafes of 19 March 2025
427 and 21 January 2026, and 3) a meeting organised in response to feedback from the
428 Collaboration Café with invited reviewers (23 April 2025). The project is currently also in the
429 process of receiving institutional ethical approval from the University of Aruba.

430 All participants will receive information about the study, its aim, the conditions of
431 participation, their right to withdraw, and guaranteed confidentiality of data. Participants
432 will have the opportunity to ask the interviewer any questions they may have and will sign
433 an informed consent form (**Appendix E**) before the interview. Participants will be informed
434 that their data will be audio recorded and pseudonymized when transcribed, meaning they
435 cannot be identified without additional information, unless they have explicitly given
436 permission to share identifiable transcripts.

437 Where possible, and if explicit consent is given, public sharing of interview and focus group
438 transcripts will be undertaken. Interview transcripts may be shared either identifiable or
439 anonymously, depending on the consent provided. Participants will have the opportunity
440 to redact or remove any data they do not wish to include.

441 In addition to the transcripts, our reflexivity notes (**Appendix A**) will be publicly shared in
442 the Stage 2 report. No identifiable information about participants will therefore be present
443 in this documentation, and paraphrasing will be used where necessary to preserve context
444 and meaning without revealing identities.

445 3 Analysis

446 Data will be analysed and described at each research stage (survey, focus groups) once
447 finalised, and may be referred to in the discussion, where findings from the reflexive
448 thematic analysis will be compared with those from earlier stages. Each method will
449 produce different types of data with distinct privacy considerations (**Table 1**).

450 **Table 2.** Levels of processing in access for this study, based on Table 3 in Branney et al. (2023).

Data	Level of processing	Storage	Level of Access
Videorecordings of interviews and focus groups	0 - raw data, all identifiers included	Proton Drive	B - Restricted
Transcripts (interviews and focus groups)	0 - raw data, all identifiers included	Proton Drive	B - Restricted or A - Open, if consent is given for individual interviews
Selected quotes from transcripts	1 - redaction of direct identifiers or 0 - raw data, all identifiers included where consent has been given	Proton Drive, eventually included in Registered Report	A - Open
De-identified transcripts	1 - redaction of direct identifiers	Proton Drive, shared via Zenodo where consent is given	A - Open where consent is given or B - Restricted where no consent is given
Survey responses	1 - redaction of direct identifiers	Google Drive, with results moved to Proton Drive.	A - Open
Theme descriptions	4 - thematic analysis (<i>keeping in mind: 0 - named quotes for which permission has been given</i>)	Proton Drive (original draft) and Google Drive for collaboration, eventually included in the Registered Report.	A - Open

451

452 3.1 Survey

453 The survey questions are designed to provide primarily quantitative data, which will be
454 analysed using descriptive statistics, cross-tabulations and figures.

455 A limited number of open-ended questions are included to complement the quantitative
456 data with qualitative insights. If substantial qualitative data are collected reflexive
457 thematic analysis will be used for analysis, following the approach described in Section
458 3.2. Where participants complete the second section of the survey (demographic data),
459 relationships between demographic variables and responses will also be examined.

460 The survey results will be used to structure the first online focus discussion and may result
461 in the adaptation of the interview questions.

462 [detailed analysis/results placeholder]

463 3.2 Interviews

464 Transcripts from the semi-structured interviews will be analysed using reflexive thematic
465 analysis, following a combined approach drawing on the six-step approach from Braun &
466 Clarke (2006; 2021; see also Byrne, 2022) and Fryer’s (2022) critical realist approach.
467 Following Fryer (2022), codes will focus on the experiences by participants, while themes
468 will aim to develop causal explanations of these experiences and events. As Fryer (2022)
469 argues, “*the three critical realist concepts of experiences, events and causes roughly*
470 *correspond to data, codes, and themes. The experiences of people remain in the data*
471 *itself, the codes consolidate these experiences to talk of events, and themes consider the*
472 *causal mechanisms that produce these events and experiences*”. Reflexive thematic
473 analysis is particularly suited to this study given its flexibility within a critical realist
474 framework and its capacity to generate rich, interpretive insights from participants' lived
475 experiences. Furthermore, as both authors are members of The Turing Way community,
476 the approach's explicit foregrounding of researcher positionality allows for the necessary
477 self-reflection and acknowledgement of the subjective roles we occupy within both the
478 community and this study.

- 479 1. Familiarising with the dataset: Reviewing the survey and focus group data,
480 focussing on the experiences by participants and the events of interest to the
481 research questions. Transcription of the interviews, (re-)reading the data and noting
482 initial ideas for codes.
- 483 2. Coding: The transcripts will be coded descriptively (both latent and semantic
484 coding) systematically, using Qualcoder (Curtain & Dröge, 2024).
- 485 3. Generating initial themes: Identifying clusters of codes with similar meanings that
486 may provide broader candidate themes that address the research questions.
- 487 4. Developing and reviewing themes: The authors discuss and check the themes,
488 reflecting on how their role as a community member may have influenced the
489 theme development.
- 490 5. Defining and naming themes: Ongoing analysis to refine the specific and
491 boundaries of each theme, generating clear definitions and names for each theme.
492 These results will be discussed in the second focus group, after which further
493 refining may be needed.
- 494 6. Producing the report: The analysis is finalized by telling a story with the themes
495 generated, illustrated by quotes from the data, and interpreted in relation to the
496 research questions.

497 The themes and sub-themes identified in this study will be described in detail in **Table 3**.

498 3.3 Focus groups

499 Focus group data will use the same combined approach of reflexive thematic analysis
500 (Braun & Clarke 2006; 2021) and Fryer’s (2022) critical realist approach as described in
501 more detail in 3.2. The data generated via the online focus groups will be analysed
502 separately from the survey and interview data, as focus groups generate a qualitatively
503 distinct form of knowledge that builds on collective sense-making and socially negotiated
504 meanings within the community, rather than distinct individual lived experiences. The
505 focus group findings will therefore inform and contextualise the broader discussion,
506 informing the next stages of the research, rather than being directly compared with the
507 other datasets.

508 *[placeholder focus group data and analysis]*

509 4. Discussion

510 *Note for limitations: Recommendations from these observations may not apply once the*
511 *community stabilises again after the loss of institutional funding from The Alan Turing Institute.*

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529 References

- 530 Alexy, O., & Leitner, M. (2011). A Fistful of Dollars: Are Financial Rewards a Suitable
531 Management Practice for Distributed Models of Innovation? *European Management*
532 *Review*, 8(3), 165–185. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1740-4762.2011.01017.x>
- 533 Atiq, A., & Tripathi, A. (2016). *Impact of Financial Benefits on Open Source Software*
534 *Sustainability*. Thirty Seventh International Conference on Information Systems,
535 Dublin 2016.
- 536 Baker, S. E., & Edwards, R. (2012). *How many qualitative interviews is enough? Expert*
537 *voices and early career reflections on sampling and cases in qualitative research*
538 [National Centre for Research Methods Review Paper]. National Centre for
539 Research Methods.
- 540 Bhaskay, R. (2016). *Enlightened Common Sense—The Philosophy of Critical Realism*.
541 Routledge.
- 542 Branney, P. E., Brooks, J., Kilby, L., Newman, K., Norris, E., Pownall, M., Talbot, C. V.,
543 Treharne, G. J., & Whitaker, C. M. (2023). Three steps to open science for qualitative
544 research in psychology. *Social and Personality Psychology Compass*, 17(4),
545 e12728. <https://doi.org/10.1111/spc3.12728>
- 546 Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2021). One size fits all? What counts as quality practice in
547 (reflexive) thematic analysis? *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 18(3), 328–352.
548 <https://doi.org/10.1080/14780887.2020.1769238>
- 549 Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2022). *Thematic Analysis: A practical guide*. SAGE Publications.

550 Buytaert, D. (2019). The privilege of free time in Open Source. Dries Buytaert.
551 <https://dri.es/the-privilege-of-free-time-in-open-source> (accessed 6 April 2026).

552 Byrne, D. (2022). A worked example of Braun and Clarke’s approach to reflexive thematic
553 analysis. *Quality & Quantity*, 56(3), 1391–1412. [https://doi.org/10.1007/s11135-](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11135-021-01182-y)
554 [021-01182-y](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11135-021-01182-y)

555 Crouse, T., & Lowe, P. A. (2018). Snowball Sampling. In B. B. Frey (Ed.), *The SAGE*
556 *Encyclopedia of Educational Research, Measurement, and Evaluation*. SAGE
557 Publications, Inc. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781506326139.n636>

558 Curtain, C., & Dröge, K. (2024). *QualCoder* (Version 3.6) [Computer software].
559 <https://github.com/ccbogel/QualCoder/releases/tag/3.6>

560 Dias, L. F., Steinmacher, I., & Pinto, G. (2018). Who drives company-owned OSS projects:
561 Internal or external members? *Journal of the Brazilian Computer Society*, 24(1), 16.
562 <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13173-018-0079-x>

563 Dryden, A. (2013). The ethics of unpaid labor and the OSS community. Ashe Dryden.
564 [https://www.ashedryden.com/blog/the-ethics-of-unpaid-labor-and-the-oss-](https://www.ashedryden.com/blog/the-ethics-of-unpaid-labor-and-the-oss-community)
565 [community](https://www.ashedryden.com/blog/the-ethics-of-unpaid-labor-and-the-oss-community) (accessed 6 April 2026).

566 Eghbal, N. (2020). Working in Public: The making and maintenance of open source
567 software. Stripe Press.

568 Frey, B. S., & Jegen, R. (2001). Motivation Crowding Theory. *Journal of Economic Surveys*,
569 15(5), 589–611. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-6419.00150>

570 Fryer, T. (2022). A critical realist approach to thematic analysis: producing causal
571 explanations. *Journal of Critical Realism*, 21(4), 365–384.
572 <https://doi.org/10.1080/14767430.2022.2076776>

573 Greenhalgh, J., & Manzano, A. (2022). Understanding ‘context’ in realist evaluation and
574 synthesis. *International Journal of Social Research Methodology*, 25(5), 583–595.
575 <https://doi.org/10.1080/13645579.2021.1918484>

576 Handcock, M. S., & Gile, K. J. (2011). Comment: On the Concept of Snowball Sampling.
577 *Sociological Methodology*, 41(1), 367–371. [https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9531.2011.01243.x)
578 [9531.2011.01243.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9531.2011.01243.x)

579 Heath, M. (2025). A Report on Burnout in Open Source Software Communities.
580 https://mirandaheath.website/static/oss_burnout_report_mh_25.pdf

581 Jahn, L., Engelbutzeder, P., Randall, D., Bollmann, Y., Ntouros, V., Michel, L. K., & Wulf, V.
582 (2024). In Between Users and Developers: Serendipitous Connections and
583 Intermediaries in Volunteer-Driven Open-Source Software Development.
584 *Proceedings of the CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, 1–
585 15. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3613904.3642541>

586 Krishnamurthy, S., Ou, S., & Tripathi, A. K. (2014). Acceptance of monetary rewards in open
587 source software development. *Research Policy*, 43(4), 632–644.
588 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2013.10.007>

589 Lakhani, K. R., & Wolf, R. G. (2005). Why hackers do what they do: Understanding
590 motivation and effort in Free/Open Source Software projects. In *Perspectives on*
591 *Free and Open Source Software* (pp. 3–21).

592 Lange, R. A., Gibson, A., Trujillo, M. Z., & Welles, B. F. (2025). Invisible Labor: The Backbone
593 of Open Source Software (Version 1). arXiv.
594 <https://doi.org/10.48550/ARXIV.2503.13405>

595 Maxwell, J., A. (2012). *A realist approach for qualitative research*. SAGE Publications.

596 Meluso, J., Casari, A., McLaughlin, K., & Trujillo, M. Z. (2025). Invisible Labor in Open
597 Source Software Ecosystems. *Proceedings of the ACM on Human-Computer*
598 *Interaction*, 9(7), 1–32. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3757417>

599 Olmos-Vega, F. M., Stalmeijer, R. E., Varpio, L., & Kahlke, R. (2023). A practical guide to
600 reflexivity in qualitative research: AMEE Guide No. 149. *Medical Teacher*, 45(3),
601 241–251. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0142159X.2022.2057287>

602 Pinto, G., Steinmacher, I., & Gerosa, M. A. (2016). More Common Than You Think: An In-
603 depth Study of Casual Contributors. *2016 IEEE 23rd International Conference on*
604 *Software Analysis, Evolution, and Reengineering (SANER)*, 112–123.
605 <https://doi.org/10.1109/SANER.2016.68>

606 Riehle, D., Riemer, P., Kolassa, C., & Schmidt, M. (2014). Paid vs. Volunteer Work in Open
607 Source. *2014 47th Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences*, 3286–
608 3295. <https://doi.org/10.1109/HICSS.2014.407>

609 Roberts, J. A., Hann, I.-H., & Slaughter, S. A. (2006). Understanding the Motivations,
610 Participation, and Performance of Open Source Software Developers: A
611 Longitudinal Study of the Apache Projects. *Management Science*, 52(7), 984–999.
612 <https://doi.org/10.1287/mnsc.1060.0554>

613 Shah, S. K. (2006). Motivation, Governance, and the Viability of Hybrid Forms in Open
614 Source Software Development. *Management Science*, 52(7), 1000–1014.
615 <https://doi.org/10.1287/mnsc.1060.0553>

616 The Turing Way Community. (2025a). Acknowledging Contributors. In *The Turing Way*.
617 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3233853>

618 The Turing Way Community. (2025b). Code of Conduct. In *The Turing Way*.
619 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3233853>

620 The Turing Way Community. (2025c). Contributing to The Turing Way. In *The Turing Way*.
621 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3233853>

622 The Turing Way Community. (2025d, June). The Turing Way Community Forum June 2025
623 [Video recording]. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=HdpWr3Y0kac>

624 The Turing Way Community & Scriberia. (2020). Illustrations from the Turing Way book
625 dashes [Graphic]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.3695300>

626 Von Krogh, G., Haefliger, S., Spaeth, S., & Wallin, M. W. (2012). Carrots and Rainbows:
627 Motivation and Social Practice in Open Source Software Development. *MIS*
628 *Quarterly*, 36(2), 649–676. <https://doi.org/10.2307/41703471>

629 Walsh, R. (2003). The methods of reflexivity. *The Humanistic Psychologist*, 31(4), 51–66.
630 <https://doi.org/10.1080/08873267.2003.9986934>

631 Willis, M. E. H. (2023). Critical realism and qualitative research in psychology. *Qualitative*
632 *Research in Psychology*, 20(2), 265–288.
633 <https://doi.org/10.1080/14780887.2022.2157782>

634 Wu, C.-G., Gerlach, J. H., & Young, C. E. (2011). The Influence of Open Source Software
635 Volunteer Developers' Motivations and Attitudes on Intention to Contribute:
636 *International Journal of Open Source Software and Processes*, 3(4), 24–48.
637 <https://doi.org/10.4018/jossp.2011100102>

638 Zhang, Y., Qin, M., Stol, K.-J., Zhou, M., & Liu, H. (2024). How Are Paid and Volunteer Open
639 Source Developers Different? A Study of the Rust Project. *Proceedings of the*
640 *IEEE/ACM 46th International Conference on Software Engineering*, 1–13.
641 <https://doi.org/10.1145/3597503.3639197>

642

643

644 Appendices

645 Appendix A – Reflexivity

646 In line with Walsh’s (2003) framework four reflexive processes are considered in this study:
647 personal, interpersonal, methodological and contextual.

648 A1 Personal reflexivity

649 Personal reflexivity is a reflection on researcher expectations, assumptions, and
650 conscious and unconscious reactions to contexts, participants, and data (Olmos-Vega et
651 al., 2023; Walsh, 2003).

652 *Esther Plomp*

653 I (Esther Plomp) am the primary investigator in the study, conducted as part of my Software
654 Sustainability Institute (SSI) Fellowship (2025-2026). I currently work as a Research
655 Developer/Post-Doc at the University of Aruba, and was previously one of the Data
656 Stewards at the Delft University in the Netherlands. I hold expertise in topics such as Open
657 Science, Research Data Management, FAIR principles, and have therefore mainly been
658 involved in The Turing Way to exchange expertise about these topics. I hold social privilege
659 as a non-disabled white woman born and raised in an EU context, with my political and
660 ideological commitments leaning towards the left as I believe in equal rights.

661 The leading role of myself in this project was discussed and communicated to the
662 community via the GitHub issue ([#3833](#)), discussed during the discussion sessions around
663 this research project, on Slack and during Collaboration Cafés. As a member of The Turing
664 Way since 2020, the research idea arose from my personal experiences and observations
665 within the community, including experiences from my (partially) funded position where
666 contributions to The Turing Way were (partially) included in my working hours (at both
667 positions held at the Delft University of Technology in the Netherlands and the University of
668 Aruba in Aruba). I was interested in how others are enabled in their contributions to The
669 Turing Way in a similar manner, and if they viewed this as sufficient enough compensation
670 for their work so that contributions are sustained for the long term. For example, while
671 some of my contributions were institutionally supported, it always felt as if I was still
672 mostly contributing on a volunteer basis as the majority of my contributions took place
673 outside of working hours. While employers were supportive of my The Turing Way related
674 work, the work was never prioritised at the same levels as other work tasks. The SSI
675 Fellowship allowed me to dedicate more time to this topic, as the Fellowship focuses on
676 exploring the differences between volunteer and paid positions in The Turing Way. The SSI

677 Fellowship did not include payment for hours dedicated to The Turing Way contributions or
678 the writing of this article (up to Stage 1).

679 The first moment of personal reflexivity focussed on considering that I have assumptions
680 about what is to be considered a paid compensation, and peers in The Turing Way may
681 view this topic very differently. As a result, the initial survey questions needed to be
682 adjusted and focus on what our community views as a ‘paid’ contribution, instead of
683 immediately divining into the details of what impact paid contributions have on community
684 dynamics.

685 *Denise Bianco*

686 I (Denise Bianco) currently work as a Senior Research Community Manager at The Alan
687 Turing Institute, while pursuing a PhD at the University of the Arts London, where I also
688 teach in the MA Innovation Management program. I hold expertise in areas such as cross-
689 disciplinary scientific collaborations, science-of-team science, community building, and
690 qualitative research. I am a white woman at mid-career stage, born and raised in an EU
691 context, so I recognise the potential for blind spots in my approach.

692 My research work is positioned at the intersection of different knowledge and practice
693 domains, investigating art–science relations as part of my doctoral project and the
694 biomedical data science ecosystem as part of my work at Turing. I am strongly committed
695 to advancing diversity, equity, and inclusion in scientific research, and I champion the
696 principles of open, transparent, and reproducible science. I am a member of The Turing
697 Way, having joined first in June 2023 as a Book Dash participant and member of the Book
698 Dash Planning Committee. I have participated in two more Book Dashes since, contributed
699 two chapters to The Turing Way Book, and engaged in discussion sessions both on Slack
700 and during Collaboration Cafés. While I have never had time specifically allocated to
701 contribute to The Turing Way, my contributions were mostly included in my working hours
702 when they aligned with my work.

703

704 *[to be updated with further reflections after data are analysed]*

705

706 **A2 Interpersonal reflexivity**

707 Interpersonal reflexivity refers to how the relationships surrounding the research process
708 influence the context, people involved, and results (Walsh, 2003).

709 I (Esther Plomp) am an insider of The Turing Way Community since 2020, and consequently
710 the interactions were influenced by my experiences as a project member, chair of working

711 groups and long-term contributor. Being a known community member facilitates access to
712 participants. It also meant I had to put aside any pre-existing differences of opinions about
713 the topic, and consider existing power dynamics. The fact that I am a ‘senior’ community
714 member might be intimidating to some community members. Acknowledging that this may
715 indeed be the case, an external community member (Yanina Bellini Saibene) was asked to
716 step in in case people were not happy to discuss this topic with myself but still wanted to
717 contribute their experience to the research project. Even if people may not feel intimidated,
718 they might still decide to highlight more positive experiences to avoid negative encounters.
719 To reflect on these power dynamics and their consequences during the research process
720 Esther will take notes after every interview to consider how the power dynamics between
721 the researcher and participant could have influenced the participant’s accounts.

722 I (Denise Bianco) have been an insider of The Turing Way community since mid 2023. I
723 joined the community after author EP, and I have never held roles such as chair of working
724 groups or other leadership positions. As such, I believe our positions and perspectives
725 complement each other well, as we approach the research topics from different angles
726 influenced by our own personal experiences. It is also worth noting that I joined EP as a co-
727 author on this project in January 2026. While I was informed about the project from the very
728 start and could provide input and feedback, I was not fully involved in its initial setup.

729 **A3 Methodological reflexivity**

730 Methodological reflexivity requires critical consideration of the impacts of methodological
731 decisions (Walsh, 2003).

732 The authors take a critical realism-contextualist approach.

733 While Esther Plomp has some experience with survey and interview analysis, this will be
734 the first qualitative research project led and conducted. This entailed a time consuming
735 learning process, which resulted in an extension of the original research project planning
736 (from 2025 to the beginning of 2026, to a new timeline including 2026 for data analysis).

737 **A4 Contextual reflexivity**

738 Contextual reflexivity evaluates the cultural and historical context of a project (Walsh,
739 2003).

740 The Turing Way is a unique open source project that received institutional support from
741 several institutions by allowing community members to contribute during their working
742 time. The Turing Way aims to be an inclusive open source/science project, reflected by the
743 accessibility of the contribution guidelines and the Code of Conduct which is upheld by the
744 community.

745 The Turing Way was founded by Dr. Kirstie Whitaker in 2019, the project team included
746 researchers, librarians, data scientists and Research Engineers, from both The Alan Turing
747 Turing and the institutes across the UK and was funded by The Alan Turing Institute. The
748 project has its roots in the [Mozilla Open Leadership](#), a programme that led to Kirstie's
749 Mozilla Fellowship in 2016, which influenced her as a researcher and strengthened her
750 commitment to working openly, joined by Dr. Malvika Sharan in 2019 as the community
751 manager. Malvika expanded the project and helped to incubate what are now key
752 partnerships for *The Turing Way* within the wider 'open science' ecosystem.

753 **Development and Growth (2019-2021)**

754 This period corresponded with the COVID-19 pandemic lockdowns, which transitioned
755 many processes of contribution, collaboration, and documentation into remote ones. For
756 many, it also became clear that reproducibility on its own is not sufficient to address the
757 major challenges (including incentive challenges!) faced by research data scientists. In
758 part due to all these factors, *The Turing Way* was able to expand greatly, from one guide on
759 reproducibility into five different guides related to project design, communication,
760 collaboration, and research ethics.

761 A global (and multilingual) community began to engage with *The Turing Way*, and the
762 process of [translation/localisation](#) began informally. A [Community Handbook](#) was also
763 established to document best practices that could be used by other communities. The
764 [Fireside Chat series](#) was established in 2021, facilitating shared spaces with networks and
765 allies from across the open science ecosystem. The project received a few awards &
766 citations in the 2021 London Mayor report, HiddenREF Awards, and Goldacre Report. The
767 Book Dash Planning Committee was established in 2022 to plan the community's flagship
768 collaboration event.

769 **Maintenance and Governance (2022-2025)**

770 In 2022, Malvika and Kirstie became co-leads of *The Turing Way*, and welcomed Anne Lee
771 Steele as the new Research Community Manager.

772 As the number of contributors to the project has grown to over 400 people, *The Turing Way*
773 has also developed into a "[community of communities](#)". Many ongoing projects have been
774 developing alongside the expansion of the guides, demonstrating the need for internal
775 systems that enable the sustainability and maintenance of the project more broadly. Initial
776 governance work began in 2022 with hybrid hubs hosting Book Dash events across
777 multiple geographic locations and working groups developed to formalise localisation and
778 translation, reviewing & editing, training and mentorship, accessibility, and infrastructure

779 within the project. The number of talks and workshops given by community members also
780 expanded.

781 In 2023, *The Turing Way* delivery team expanded, with the addition of Alexandra Araujo
782 Alvarez as TTW's first Project Manager. [The Practitioner's Hub](#) was piloted with the first
783 cohort of 5 Experts-in-Residence (EiR). The open infrastructure of the project has also
784 expanded, as *The Turing Way* moved to a separate [Github organisation](#).

785 **Sustainability of the project and contributors (2024 and onwards)**

786 In 2024 and 2025 governance of the project to ensure sustainability became increasingly
787 important, as in 2025 the project lost the direct financial support from the Alan Turing
788 institute, resulting in the loss of the Community Manager and Project Manager, as well as
789 several researchers that moved to different research institutes.

790 **The Turing Way tools**

791 *The Turing Way* has been funded by The Alan Turing Institute since the very beginning.
792 Because the project is open source, executable, and a prior relationship existed, the book
793 was written and published using JupyterBook. A GitHub repository was made for the
794 project, and internal processes decided in how to acknowledge authorship works within
795 the project (for example with the usage of bots, such as the Welcome bot and All-
796 Contributors bot) and collaborative spaces and events (both online and in-person) to
797 contribute to the guides were created (such as the Collaboration Cafe and Book Dash).

798

799 **A5 Reflexivity Journal**

800 Questions for reflections:

- 801 ● Why *might* I be having this particular type of response, and how *might* this matter for
802 my research?
- 803 ● How did power dynamics between the researcher and participant influence the
804 participant's account?
- 805 ● Have I sought sufficient criticism on my interpretation of the data?

806

807 **A6 Reflexivity meetings**

808 During the study Esther Plomp and Denise Bianco will meet regularly to document relevant
809 thoughts, interpretations and decisions in this Appendix. Minimally, the following meetings
810 will take place:

- 811 A6.1 Before survey
- 812 A6.2 After survey and before first focus group
- 813 A6.3 After focus group, before interviews
- 814 A6.4 After interviews, before second focus group
- 815 A6.5 After second focus group
- 816 A6.6 After finalizing the draft Stage 2 Registered Report
- 817
- 818

819 Appendix B1 – Survey Introduction and Questions

820 You are being asked to participate in a research study conducted by Esther Plomp and
821 Denise Bianco, on behalf of The Turing Way and in the context of Esther’s SSI Fellowship.
822 This survey is intended to identify what The Turing Way community members consider as
823 ‘being a compensated contributor’, so that we can better understand how contributions to
824 the book and community are facilitated, as well as any resulting dynamics within the
825 community.

826 Participation in the research is voluntary, and the decision to participate or not will have no
827 impact on your relationship with The Turing Way community. For the full ethical
828 procedures of this study, please see: <https://hackmd.io/u8du8QjbSh-G1oIAjIB8lQ>. For any
829 questions, please contact Esther (esther.plomp@ua.aw).

830

831 **Section 1: In what capacity do you contribute to The Turing Way?**

832 **Have you engaged with The Turing Way before?** (*Tick all that apply*)

- 833 • I have read the book or used it in my work
- 834 • I shared content of the book or community activities with others
- 835 • I joined Slack and/or engaged with discussions on Slack
- 836 • I have contributed to the book via GitHub (*opening up an issue, pull request,*
837 *engaging with other’s issues/PRs, reviewing or contributing to a GitHub discussion*)
- 838 • I have joined events, such as Community Calls, Collaboration Cafés, Fireside Chat,
839 or a Book Dash
- 840 • I took leadership roles in a working group or in the organisation of an event
- 841 • I haven't engaged with The Turing Way at all before encountering this survey
- 842 • Other, please describe

843

844 **Approximately how often do you normally engage with The Turing Way?**

845

- 846 • Daily
- 847 • Several times a week

- 848 • Once a week
- 849 • Several times a month
- 850 • Once a month
- 851 • Several times a year
- 852 • Annually
- 853 • Never

854

855 **To what degree are your engagements with The Turing Way financially supported?**
856 (check all that apply)

- 857 • I contribute in my free time with limited financial support from other sources
- 858 • I contribute in my free time with sufficient financial support from other sources
- 859 • I could contribute during working hours as my contributions could be counted as
860 part of my work activities, but due to other priorities I normally contribute in my free
861 time instead
- 862 • I contribute during working hours as my contributions are part of my work activities
863 or externally funded by a research grant
- 864 • Other, please describe

865

866 **Which types of recognition or compensation have you received for your contributions**
867 **to The Turing Way book or community?**

- 868 • Received thanks or written/verbal acknowledgement of the work
- 869 • Received feedback on something I worked on for the community/book that
870 improved the work
- 871 • Developed (professional) relationships
- 872 • Developed skills (*GitHub, collaboration, project management, event organization*)
- 873 • Brought opportunities for exposure or recognition in my other
874 professional communities
- 875 • Increased professional status
- 876 • Was able to use the experience in a grant proposal

- 877 • Was able to use the experience on a CV
- 878 • Received The Turing Way gifts (*such as socks, stickers, chocolate*)
- 879 • Received compensation for event attendance (*accessibility, mobility, internet or*
- 880 *subsistence budget*)
- 881 • Reviewed formal recognition from work (*contributions are discussed in annual*
- 882 *reviews, prioritised during working hours*)
- 883 • Received salary
- 884 • Other, please describe

885

886 **Do you think that your contributions to The Turing Way are adequately recognised and**

887 **rewarded? Please elaborate on how your contributions are recognised (or not) by both**

888 **The Turing Way Community and your employer (if this is relevant).**

889

890 **Section 2/ Wrap up and possible follow up for semi-structured interview.**

891 *Please note that any information that you provide here is personally identifiable and can be*

892 *linked to your answers in section 1. As you are currently filling out a Google Form it also*

893 *means that Google will have access to this personally identifiable information. If you'd*

894 *rather not be identifiable and/or share this information with Google you do not have to fill*

895 *out this part of the survey to participate in the research. If you would still like to participate*

896 *in the semi-structured interviews you can always reach out to Esther separately instead of*

897 *adding your details here.*

898 **What is your gender?**

- 899 • Non binary
- 900 • Woman
- 901 • Man
- 902 • Prefer to self describe:

903 **How would you describe your racial or ethnic identity?**

904 *There is substantial variation in how people think about race and ethnicity around the*

905 *world. Do any of these response options describe your racial or ethnic identity? If so, select*

906 *all that apply. If not, please provide your racial or ethnic identity in "Prefer to use a different*

907 *term." If you do not have a racial or ethnic identity, select "Non-identifying."*

- 908 • Asian
- 909 • Black or African American
- 910 • Hispanic or Latino
- 911 • Middle Eastern or North African
- 912 • Native or other Indigenous Peoples
- 913 • Pacific Islander
- 914 • White or Caucasian
- 915 • Prefer to use a different term (fill in the blank)
- 916 • Non-identifying
- 917 • Prefer not to answer

918 **What is your current geographic location?**

919 **Have you contributed to The Turing Way from any other geographic locations?**

920

921 **Please indicate here if you consent to being contacted in the future to discuss your**
922 **answers to the survey in more detail** (via a semi-structured interview of approximately
923 45-60 minutes)

924 Yes - I have provided my email:

925 No

926

927 **B2 - First draft version of the survey before feedback in the April**
928 **2025 meeting**

929 **Section 1 - Demographics**

930 *This section will be used in conjunction with other sections to help us to understand how*
931 *attitudes and practices in The Turing Way differ across different fields, roles, and career*
932 *stages.*

933 Of the options below, which best describes your job role?

- 934 • Undergraduate or Masters Student
- 935 • PhD Candidate
- 936 • Postdoctoral Researcher or Fellow
- 937 • Lecturer
- 938 • (Assistant/Associate/Full) Professor
- 939 • Research Software Engineer
- 940 • Senior Team or Department Leader
- 941 • Research Infrastructure Role (Technician, Community Manager, Data Manager and
942 so forth)

943 • Other (please describe in the box below)

944 Of these options below, which of the following career stages best describes you?

945 • Junior

946 • Mid-level

947 • Senior

948 • Other (please describe)

949 Do you consider yourself to be a Turing Way community member? *(Tick all that apply)*

950 • Yes, I engage with discussions on Slack

951 • Yes, I have contributed to the book via GitHub

952 • Yes, I have participated in events, such as Community Calls, Collaboration Cafés or
953 a Book Dash

954 • Yes, I took leadership roles in a working group or in the organisation of an event

955 • No, I haven't engaged with The Turing Way at all before opening up this survey

956 Do you consider yourself to be primarily a volunteer or paid contributor to The Turing Way

957 • Volunteer (I contribute in my free-time)

958 • Paid (contributing to The Turing Way is part of my position)

959 • Both

960 • I'm not sure

961 What time-period are you keeping in mind when you are answering this survey? *(If you were*
962 *both a volunteer and paid contributor in different time periods, you have the option to*
963 *answer the survey twice!)*

964 Approximately how often do you contribute to The Turing Way (Community or Book) during
965 an average work week?

966 *A contribution includes a discussion on Slack, GitHub, opening of an Issue/PR, or attending*
967 *an event.*

968 • Daily

969 • Several times a week

970 • Once a week

971 • Several times a month

972 • Once a month

973 • Several times a year

974 • Annually

- 975 • Never
- 976 • Other (please describe)

977 **Section 2: Barriers and opportunities for contributors**

978 Do you think that your contributions are adequately recognised and rewarded?

- 979 • Yes
- 980 • No

981 From your perspective, what are the main barriers to contributing to The Turing Way? (if
982 time is the main barrier you are experiencing, what other barriers are also there so that you
983 cannot make the time to contribute?)

984 Would receiving some sort of payment or compensation remove those barriers? What
985 payment or compensation method would you prefer?

986 How easy is it for paid contributors to contribute to the community/book? (1-5)

987 How easy is it for paid contributors to take leadership roles in the community? (1-5)

988 How easy is it for volunteer contributors to contribute to the community/book? (1-5)

989 How easy is it for volunteer contributors to take leadership roles in the community? (1-5)

990 Do you feel like paid contributors have more say in what happens in the community?
991 (1-5)

992 Can you elaborate your answer on the ease of contribution to the community for volunteer
993 and paid contributors?

994 Do you think paid contributors are a requirement for the sustainability of the Community?

- 995 • Yes
- 996 • No
- 997 • Not sure

998 **Section 3 / Wrap up and possible follow up for semi-structured interview.**

999 Please indicate here if you consent to being contacted in the future to discuss your
1000 answers to the survey in more detail

1001 Yes - I have provided my email above

1002 No

1003 Please suggest any names of other Turing Way community members that could contribute

1004 to the project (We particularly welcome suggestions for individuals that disengaged with

1005 the project)

1006

1007 Appendix C – Semi-structured Interview Questions

1008 Optional demographic data

1009 • Where in the world are you currently based in

1010 • Gender

1011 Non optional data:

1012 • **Tell me about your involvement with the Turing Way community?**

1013 ○ Why do you contribute?

1014 ○ What got you interested in the community? What has kept you engaged?

1015 ○ What has been difficult when trying to contribute to The Turing Way?

1016 • **Volunteer/paid contributor**

1017 ○ What do you see as ‘being compensated’? (any difference with being paid?)

1018 • **Do you feel adequately compensated for your efforts in The Turing Way?**

1019 ○ What do you see as adequate compensation?

1020 ○ Could you tell me more about that (when, how it happened, what it entailed -
1021 such as positive impact career/development and so forth)

1022 ○ Why do you see that as a success? Why do you see it as a failure?

1023 • **Do you feel positively impacted for your efforts in The Turing Way?**

1024 ○ Could you tell me more about that (when, how it happened, what it entailed -
1025 such as positive impact career/development and so forth)

1026 ○ Why do you see that as a success? Why do you see it as a failure?

1027 • **Do you feel like it makes a difference to be a volunteer or paid member to
1028 contribute to the Community?**

1029 ○ Does it make a difference in leadership roles?

1030 • How does paid contribution relate to the sustainability of the community?

1031 • **What could the Turing Way do to facilitate contributions to the community?**

1032 ○ How can community development be improved?

1033 ○ What does the community need more of?

1034 ○ What does the community need less of?

1035 ● Is there anything that we haven't discussed?

1036

1037 Appendix D – Focus Groups (placeholder)

1038

1039 Appendix E – Full Ethics Procedure

1040

1041 Contact persons:

- 1042 ● Arielle Bennett, Senior Researcher, Open Source Practices, Tools, Practices &
1043 Systems, abennett@turing.ac.uk
- 1044 ● **SSI Fellow, Esther Plomp**, is a member of The Turing Way and will coordinate the
1045 project and is primarily responsible for all deliverables and outcomes.

1046 These ethical materials have been based on ethical procedures followed by [JupyterHub](#)
1047 [/Organisational Mycology](#), available under a CC-BY 4.0 License.

1048 D1. Purpose and Aims of Research

1049 Esther Plomp has received a SSI Fellowship (2025-2026) that focuses on how contributions
1050 to The Turing Way can be facilitated, with a particular distinction made between
1051 contributions by volunteers and contributions by paid members. The project is also
1052 supported in-kind by the University of Aruba. The project wants to conduct a survey (co-
1053 created with Turing Way community members via a focus group session during a
1054 Collaboration Cafe), followed up with a focus group and in-depth semi-structured
1055 interviews with members and contributors of The Turing Way. As this study involves human
1056 participants and collection of personal data, and may have an impact on The Turing Way
1057 community (by individuals donating their time and potentially their personal data) I am
1058 seeking ethical approval from The Turing Way community. The project will be conducted as
1059 openly as possible, with data collection efforts and preliminary findings shared with the
1060 community as openly and quickly as possible.

1061 This study is intended to:

- 1062 ● Identify what compensated contributions look like (financial compensation,
1063 training, mentoring, visibility, time?);
- 1064 ● Identify if there are any (unwanted) dynamics caused by different types of
1065 contributors (volunteer or paid);
- 1066 ● Provide the basis to support both paid and volunteer contributions to the
1067 community, informing strategies to avoid differentiation between these types of
1068 contributors;
- 1069 ● Inform the revision and improvement of the contribution processes, ensuring that
1070 contributors receive fitting compensation and acknowledgement.

1071 A major goal of the project is to ensure that The Turing Way remains an inclusive
1072 community to contributors. The project is part of a constant process of designing, learning,

1073 and refining ways of working and engaging with The Turing Way community. The resulting
1074 data may be published and reused in other projects and communities to improve
1075 contribution processes.

1076 Esther Plomp will conduct the primary research, including the survey, focus group and
1077 interviews with community members, and research on publicly available forum discussion
1078 data. Esther Plomp has been a (partially) paid contributor, thanks to institutional support
1079 of both the Faculty of Applied Sciences of the Delft University of Technology (the
1080 Netherlands) and the University of Aruba (Aruba). She takes an intermediate position
1081 between paid and volunteer contributions, potentially mitigating any power dynamics
1082 present that could impact data collection. *The Turing Way* has [resources on addressing](#)
1083 [feedback when there are power imbalances](#) which will be utilised as needed, alongside the
1084 project's [Code of Conduct](#).

1085 *D Positionality statement on biases*

1086 Bias is in many ways inevitable: Esther's identity and experience with The Turing Way
1087 community will shape the experience of the interviewees and research participants. To
1088 make the experience more comfortable participants will be reminded of their autonomy–
1089 they are free to withdraw, skip questions they find uncomfortable, challenge Esther's
1090 interpretation of particular observations or incidents, and otherwise shape their
1091 participation in ways that best reflect their true experiences.

1092 There is also the risk that people will not feel comfortable expressing critiques about
1093 leadership, as Esther is considered to be part of leadership. Participants will be provided
1094 with the option to contact a Turing Way community member that is not involved in
1095 leadership (Yanina Bellini Saibene) to express their concerns via this route, allowing for
1096 these concerns to then be expressed anonymously towards Esther and to be taken into
1097 account in the project.

1098 By continually seeking feedback on the project, the methods and results will be constantly
1099 re-evaluated and updated as needed.

1100 **D2. Details study procedure per activity**

1101 *D2.1 Survey*

1102 It is difficult to predict what the response rate of any given survey will be. The survey will be
1103 open to all The Turing Way community members who actively view the communication
1104 spaces used by the community (such as Slack, mailing lists, and GitHub). Survey
1105 respondents will range from 50 to 100 individuals. If the response rate is unexpectedly low,
1106 input will be asked from community members on individually based communication.

1107 The survey will be piloted with three individuals. These three individuals will have different
1108 backgrounds, ideally a volunteer contributor, paid contributor and someone with a mixed
1109 volunteer/paid contributor.

1110 The survey should identify:

- 1111 ● What responders to the survey are financially supported in their contributions, and
1112 whether they consider themselves as a paid or volunteer contributor.
- 1113 ● The definition of what a compensated contribution entails according to The Turing
1114 Way contributors.

1115 *D2.2 Community data on GitHub/Slack*

1116 To support survey/interview data, publicly available data from issues, pull requests and
1117 discussion posts on The Turing Way, as well as discussions on Slack, can be used to
1118 support statements made in survey/interviews. There is no plan to fully scrape or analyse
1119 all the content in the GitHub Repository/Slack.

1120 *D2.3 Semi-structured Interviews*

1121 Based on survey data several contributors will be asked to elaborate on their answers in
1122 the survey in more detail. The intention is to engage with 10-20 community members in the
1123 interview stage, 5-10 members that are a volunteer contributor, 5-10 members that are or
1124 have been paid contributors, 2-3 members that took a leadership role (contributing to a
1125 working/planning group) in the community on a volunteer basis, 2-3 members that took a
1126 leadership role on a paid basis. In addition, a balance will be strived for in terms of level of
1127 contribution experience, roles and self-reported demographics, pending on availability of
1128 community members. Participants will be asked to self-identify their role, duration and
1129 time-frame of their participation in the community.

1130 Semi-structured interviews are intended to:

- 1131 ● Refine the definition of financial support for contributions as established by the
1132 survey data;
- 1133 ● Clarify how different types of contributors feel supported or challenged when they
1134 contribute to the Turing Way;
- 1135 ● Identify in more detail what challenges contributors face and how this is related to
1136 compensation for their efforts;
- 1137 ● The impact of (direct) financial compensation on contributions, and the effect this
1138 may have long-term on the contributor/community.

1139

1140 *D2.4 Community discussion of results*

1141 The community will be involved via a discussion around this ethical procedure in the
1142 Collaboration Cafe of 19 March, as well as involved in structuring the survey questions.

1143 Furthermore, the community will be involved in other communication opportunities:

- 1144 • Survey questions will be communicated again after the focus group for further
1145 input, before the survey will be conducted.
- 1146 • Survey questions and further input will be invited during the Book Dash in May
1147 (Collaboration Workshop and online event 20-21 May)
- 1148 • The results of the study will be discussed with the community via a focus group,
1149 before being published in the form of an article.
- 1150 • Where possible, asynchronous contributions from contributors who are unable to
1151 attend events will be incorporated by sharing discussion notes and requesting
1152 responses.
- 1153 • Finally, the lessons learned will be used to improve the existing processes of The
1154 Turing Way, and will be contributed to the Book in the form of a new chapter or
1155 section so that the results and recommendations are also available for other
1156 communities.

1157 *D2.5 Article*

1158 An article will be written, which will:

- 1159 • Provide an insight into how The Turing Way community views compensation for
1160 contributions to the community
- 1161 • Document the challenges and opportunities in supporting contributors, as well as
1162 the various strategies that can be employed to ensure compensation for
1163 contributors
- 1164 • Share lessons learned
- 1165 • Describe strategies for pathways for paid/volunteer contributors

1166 **D3. Ethical Considerations**

1167 *D3.1 Project Methods and Data*

1168 The main research questions relate to The Turing Way community, therefore data
1169 collection will be focused on members of The Turing Way (community members on Slack,
1170 GitHub contributors and newsletter subscribers) to investigate the support that both paid
1171 and volunteer community members experience in contributing to The Turing Way. As the

1172 research will primarily focus on The Turing Way the results will not be generalizable. The
1173 research may be relevant to other open science/source communities, but in any
1174 dissemination of the results it will be stressed that the results are primarily applicable to
1175 The Turing Way.

1176 Data will derive from various sources, such as focus groups, discussions, public data from
1177 GitHub/Slack, a survey and semi-structured interviews, sketching an accurate picture of
1178 the processes and how they are experienced by Turing Way contributors.

1179 *D3.2 Recruitment Strategy*

1180 Community members will be asked (passively) to participate in the study via messages in
1181 the newsletter, Slack and during Community Calls. Community members will also be
1182 actively approached by directly emailing or messaging them. If members indicate that they
1183 are not interested in participation they will no longer be actively recruited.

1184 Challenges for representation will include: ensuring that community members from a
1185 variety of backgrounds, expertise levels, and involvement in the project are included in
1186 data collection; collecting data on those missing from the community, who might
1187 contribute but cannot/do not due to the existing barriers; and enabling potential
1188 participants to participate with as little interference to their day-to-day work as possible.
1189 To mitigate some of these challenges, Esther will proactively reach out to members of the
1190 community throughout the duration of the project, offer participation time slots that meet
1191 their preferences and accommodate their work and personal responsibilities.

1192 There is a majority voice missing from community surveys and forum post analysis: those
1193 that might have become contributors but did not due to structural or personal barriers so
1194 never joined the community to add their voice. Where possible, these missing contributors
1195 will be approached to ensure representation in the results.

1196 *D3.3 Diversity of Engagement*

1197 Several steps are taken to ensure engagement with a variety of people:

- 1198 ● Advertising the call for participation on all possible communication forums.
- 1199 ● Requesting that participants inform us or their peers about the opportunity to
1200 participate, particularly encouraging these participants to think about people who
1201 might have a unique or underrepresented view on the topics we cover.
- 1202 ● Attending The Turing Way Collaboration Café events to share intermediate findings
1203 and make attendees aware of opportunities to participate.

- 1204 • Seeking feedback on preliminary findings via the GitHub repository ([#3833](#)), which
1205 will include information on how to participate, and include discussions that will
1206 inform the study and affect the interview/survey questions.

1207 D4. Interviews

1208 Semi-structured interviews will be audio recorded and transcribed. Following, Thematic
1209 Analysis will be used to generate themes insights (Braun & Clarke 2022). Braun & Clarke’s
1210 (2021; 2022) framework for reflexive thematic analysis will guide the analysis of
1211 transcriptions. The purpose of thematic analysis is to develop themes in the dataset in
1212 relation to the research question (Braun & Clarke, 2022). This research takes an inductive
1213 approach (codes and themes are developed through engagement with the data rather than
1214 determined by previous research).

- 1215 • Representative quotes from interviews may be used to substantiate claims.
- 1216 • For public sharing, notes/transcripts will be structured by interviewee via a unique
1217 participant ID. Before publishing any data, participants will have the opportunity to
1218 redact or remove data they do not wish to have included. For public sharing only
1219 quotes from participants that have consented to public sharing will be used.

1220 D5. Data Management Plan

1221 *D5.1 Data provenance and procurement*

1222 The qualitative interview data and quantitative survey data used for the project will be
1223 gathered and analysed as part of SSI Fellowship of Esther Plomp, running from 2025-2026.

- 1224 • Notes and collaborative artifacts (such as photos of whiteboards, sticky notes,
1225 diagrams) will be collected from the focus groups and discussions about the
1226 project during events such as collaboration cafés or Book Dash events. The date
1227 and time of the workshops will be recorded.

1228 *D5.2 Preprocessing*

- 1229 • Interview recordings will be transcribed using Zoom/otter.ai, or using manual
1230 transcription. Transcripts will be loaded into a private Proton Drive with access only
1231 available to Esther Plomp and Denise Bianco. Transcripts will be loaded into
1232 qualitative data analysis software (QualCoder) on local machines. Transcript
1233 excerpts will be placed in a spreadsheet on the same Drive during the analysis
1234 phase.
- 1235 • Archival data will be collected and handled in the same way as interview
1236 transcripts, described above.

- 1237 • Survey data will be collected using Google Forms. Responses will be exported as a
1238 CSV file, stored in the private Google Drive before stored for the long term on a
1239 Proton drive, and analyzed on local machines.
- 1240 • Notes and collaborative artifacts from Focus Groups, Collaboration Cafes or Book
1241 Dash events will be preserved in their original form on the Proton Drive.

1242 *D5.3 Data Sharing*

- 1243 • Excerpts from the interview, archival, survey data, and event notes and artifacts will
1244 be communicated in reports and a research article. Anonymised excerpts will also
1245 be stored and shared when approved by the research participant, as described in
1246 the research participation consent form.
- 1247 • A public dataset will be shared on Zenodo for long term preservation, under a CC-
1248 BY license. This public dataset contains participant-approved excerpts from
1249 interviews and surveys. Participants who agree to have excerpts shared will have
1250 the opportunity to review and/or remove content prior to publishing. We will also
1251 include the research instruments (semi-structured interview protocol, survey
1252 questions, consent form and this ethics procedure) in the project repository, an
1253 explanation of our process for developing the instruments, a methods description
1254 for data collection and analysis, and the scope of work for this project.
- 1255 • Findings will be communicated in English.

1256 *D5.4 Storage & Security*

- 1257 • Recordings will be locally stored and transferred to a Proton Drive (storage in the
1258 EU). Once the research article is published, the recordings will be deleted.
- 1259 • Transcripts are only available to Esther Plomp and Denise Bianco. These will be
1260 stored on a private Proton Drive.
- 1261 • A private Google Drive will be used for survey data storage: participants will be
1262 informed of the risks associated with sharing their data with a Big Tech company in
1263 the survey form itself.
- 1264 • Demographic data is optionally provided. Questions about demographic data will
1265 be included as they are relevant for the experiences as a community member. This
1266 data will be monitored carefully to avoid identification of community members.

1267 **D6. Governance**

1268 Community consensus will be strived for during the project duration, with Esther Plomp
1269 making any final decisions if consensus cannot be reached. Working openly on GitHub as

1270 much as practicable offers the opportunity for audit and scrutiny by community members
1271 and stakeholders.

1272 D7. Stakeholders

1273 Main stakeholders in the project:

- 1274 • Turing Way community members
- 1275 • Turing Way leadership

1276 Peripheral stakeholders

- 1277 • Other open source community members and potential members who can benefit
1278 from more systematic analysis of where improvements can be made to the
1279 contribution pathways of open source projects.

1280 D8. Impact

1281 The overarching goal of this project is to enhance and enrich contributor communities with
1282 practical strategies for empowering a more diverse array of contributors. Central to the
1283 overarching aims of the project are concrete recommendations for process and pathway
1284 improvements which increase the overall diversity and vibrancy of The Turing Way
1285 community.

1286 We do not anticipate any significant harms that will come from the outputs of our work.
1287 Findings may possibly cause distress or discomfort to members of the community or
1288 leadership. Spaces for discussion will be facilitated to mitigate these risks and ensure that
1289 the discomfort will lead to improving the inclusion of the community.

1290 DE9. Sustainability

1291 *D9.1 Environmental sustainability*

1292 The project is not expected to generate a comparatively large amount of data or to use
1293 computationally expensive algorithms to analyse it, so the additional environmental costs
1294 of storage and compute are relatively low.

1295 The majority of the work will take place remotely via online collaboration, reducing carbon
1296 emissions from the need to travel to conduct the research, but not eliminating the
1297 environmental impact of utilising technology.

1298 **D10. Transparency**

1299 *D10.1 Process*

1300 The project has been discussed with *The Turing Way* leadership and the Community prior
1301 to work commencing. A [GitHub Issue](#) has been opened to keep track of project progress,
1302 invite feedback and present interim findings.

1303 Esther Plomp will attend community calls and collaboration cafes to discuss the project
1304 openly to enable community members to ask questions, challenge the project
1305 approaches, and discuss different aspects of the work.

1306 Project procedures are outlined in detail in the consent form for 1:1 interviews, which
1307 clearly outline the risks and benefits of the work.

1308 *D10.2 Outcome Transparency*

- 1309 ● The project intends to produce an open access research article covering the
1310 findings and recommendations from the research.
- 1311 ● De-identified data from the 1:1 interviews and survey will also be published openly
1312 under an open License on a GitHub repository (with a version shared on Zenodo).
- 1313 ● Findings and recommendations will be shared with The Turing Way leadership, so
1314 that practical changes to contributor pathways can be applied where needed.
1315 Generalisable findings will also be incorporated in the Turing Way book.

1316

1317 Appendix F – Informed Consent Form Interviews

1318 Consent Form: Participation in The Turing Way Community Research Activities

1319 SUMMARY:

1320 You are being asked to participate in a research study led by Esther Plomp on behalf of The
1321 Turing Way for her SSI Fellowship. The Turing Way has granted permission to conduct
1322 observations and interviews with community members. This research is being conducted
1323 for the purposes of evaluating and improving the Turing Way's community-building
1324 strategies, with a focus on how differential financial support may affect contributions to
1325 The Turing Way. Participation in the research is voluntary, and the decision to participate or
1326 not will have no impact on your relationship with The Turing Way community.

1327 PURPOSE:

1328 Data collection for this study is intended to:

- 1329 • Identify successes, challenges and opportunities that contributors faced when they
1330 contributed to The Turing Way
- 1331 • Identify what paid contributions look like (financial compensation, training,
1332 mentoring, visibility, time?)
- 1333 • Support contributions to the community, developing strategies to avoid
1334 differentiations between differentially supported contributors
- 1335 • Inform the revision and improvement of the contribution processes, ensuring that
1336 contributors receive fitting compensation.

1337 PROCEDURES:

1338 If you decide to participate, we will schedule a time to interview you about your
1339 experiences in and opinions of the Turing Way community. We expect the interview to last
1340 between 45 to 60 minutes. This interview will be held remotely over videoconference. The
1341 conversation will be audio-recorded for transcription, after which the audio-recording will
1342 be deleted once the research article has been published. You will be asked to review the
1343 transcript, an activity that is voluntary. Afterwards, anonymized transcripts with limited
1344 reidentification risks will be publicly published (only with consent) on Zenodo for long term
1345 preservation, under an open license to facilitate reuse. You may still participate in the
1346 study even if you do not consent to public sharing of your (anonymised) transcript.
1347 However, we will need your consent to use your data for analysis within the study. During
1348 the interview we will follow the [Turing Way Code of Conduct](#).

1349 **RISKS AND BENEFITS:**

1350 There are no major risks and benefits expected when participating in this research. If the
1351 interview is making you feel uncomfortable you can decide to close the interview at any
1352 time. You will be asked about demographic data (such as country) that will be optional to
1353 answer.

1354 Your opinions may include criticism to leadership. While leadership is actively looking for
1355 feedback to improve processes within The Turing Way, we understand if you would like to
1356 avoid any type of retaliation and prefer to contact someone other than Esther about these
1357 concerns.

- 1358 • I understand that if I want to express critique about The Turing Way and want to do
1359 so without revealing my identity to Esther, I may contact Yanina Bellini Saibene
1360 (yabellini@ropensci.org).

1361 Your data will be carefully managed. Specifically:

- 1362 • Recordings will be transcribed into text via Zoom/otter.ai or manually if participants
1363 are not comfortable using big tech solutions for these purposes. Transcripts and
1364 recordings are stored on a private Proton Drive that only the study's authors (Esther
1365 Plomp, Denise Bianco) can access.
 - 1366 ○ Yes I consent to Zoom being used to record and Zoom/otter.ai being used for
1367 transcription - meaning that Zoom/otter.ai will have access to the recording
1368 and transcription data
 - 1369 ○ No, my transcripts should be done manually- meaning that the recording is
1370 still managed by Zoom but the transcription is locally stored
 - 1371 ○ No, I do not consent to any recordings or transcription tools. Only notes may
1372 be taken.

1373 There is always a potential risk of a data breach. Risks are considered minimal as the
1374 intention of the project is to share the resulting data as transparently as possible.

1375 **CONFIDENTIALITY**

1376 Unless you grant permission to use your name, title, and/or quote you in any publications
1377 that may result from this research, the information you share will be confidential. De-
1378 identified quotes and paraphrased responses may be used in reports and other
1379 publications of the study's results.

1380 ○ Yes, I grant permission for the use of my name, title, and/or quote, in any
1381 publications, thus **revealing my identity publicly**.

1382 ○ No, I grant permission for the use of my **anonymized quote(s) only**

1383 Any information shared for future research will NOT include your name or other personal
1384 identifying information unless you provide consent for this below. The dataset including
1385 your responses will then be published on a public repository after you have had a chance
1386 to review and approve it.

1387 ○ I consent to the use of my data only for the particular study described above - the
1388 **transcripts may not be publicly shared** on Zenodo.

1389 ○ I consent to sharing the transcript of the interview in a **publicly-shared** dataset,
1390 where my data will be **anonymized**.

1391 ○ I consent to sharing the transcript of the interview in a **publicly-shared** dataset,
1392 where **my identity will be known**. As the publicly shared dataset will be shared
1393 under a CC-BY license, I understand that this means that I have no control over
1394 future data processing and reuse.

1395 If you consented to public sharing of the data, you may still withdraw this consent up until
1396 the dataset has been published on Zenodo.

1397 ○ I understand that I can withdraw my consent for either activity at any time up until
1398 the public dataset has been published on Zenodo.

1399 **DATA USE, RETENTION, AND EU-GDPR**

1400 The categories of personal data you are being asked to consent to are your name, email
1401 address, gender, geographic location, role in the Turing Way community, other
1402 employment information (such organization, role and career stage), audio recording, and
1403 qualitative descriptions of your experiences and insights from working in/engaging with the
1404 Turing Way community.

1405 Your personal data will be stored on a Proton Drive (storage in the EU).

1406 Transcripts will be anonymized. This work will be easier if you do not identify other
1407 individuals in your interview. If you forget and use names of other contributors the
1408 information will be redacted later.

1409 **QUESTIONS:**

1410 If you have any questions about this research project, wish to withdraw, please contact:
1411 Esther Plomp, esther.plomp@ua.aw, Denise Bianco dbianco@turing.ac.uk. If you have any

1412 concerns about this study, or if you think you may have been injured or harmed as a result
1413 of your participation, please contact: Arielle Bennett, abennett@turing.ac.uk.

1414 Participation in this research is voluntary. By signing, you indicate that you have decided to
1415 participate in this study and provide consent for processing your personal data. You will be
1416 given a signed copy of this form to keep.

1417 Name of Participant: _____

1418

1419

1420 Signature of Participant: _____

1421 Date: _____

1422

1423 **Appendix G – Deviations from Stage 1**

1424

1425 Table to be filled out for any changes and updates made for the Stage 2 Registered Report.

1426